

Evaluation Of The Effect Of Chronic Heavy Smoking By Pulmonary Function Test

Sajid S Saiyad *, Alkesh Vara **, Samir Bhagora ***, Dharitri Parmar****, R Dixit*****

*Tutor,****Professor and Head,Department of Physiology,*****Dean Govt., Medical College, Surat, **Assistant Professor, M.P.Shah Medical College, Jamnagar*** Assistant Professor, GMERS Medical College, Patan , Gujarat.

Abstract: Background: Pulmonary functions are significantly affected by the chronic smoking. Study has done to investigate relationships between heavy cigarette smoking (20 cigarettes/bidis per day) and pulmonary function in Adult men. Objective is to find out If Chronic heavy smoking start affecting the lung functions as early 5 years of habit. Method: A cross sectional study on 112 individuals , selected randomly from general population of Ahmedabad city was performed. A thorough history analysis (Height, Weight, BMI), Physical examinations Spirometry were done on all individuals after explaining them procedure and taking their consent. Parameters measured by the spirometer were FEV1, FVC, FEV1/FVC, PEFR, MEF75, MEF50, MEF25, VC. Result: Among the measured parameters of PFT, smokers have significantly decreased values($p < 0.05$) of FVC, FEV1, FEV1/FVC & PEFR. Conclusion: Chronic heavy smoking leads to significant decrease in pulmonary functions in smokers group, and It can be concluded that chronic smoking affects the health of the individuals. Therefore, smoking habit should be avoided for better health.

Key Words: Smokers , Nonsmokers, Pulmonary function tests, Height, Weight, Body Mass Index(BMI)

Author for correspondence: Dr.Sajid S. Saiyad, Department of Physiology, Government Medical College, Surat. E- mail: sajid.s.saiyad@gmail.com , contact no. 09426040601

Introduction: Cigarette smoking has been identified to be the most important determinant of ventilatory impairment.

Although it is known that smoking causes respiratory dysfunction, but very few works^{1,2,3} have been actually done on the dose and time dependent effect of smoking on lungs. In longitudinal studies smoking has been shown to impair the growth of forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1) in children and cause an accelerated decline in FEV1, in adults. Objective is know whether the chronic heavy smoking start deteriorating the pulmonary function test as early as 5 years of smoking habit.

Spirometry is a simple test to measure the amount of air a person can breathe in and out, and the amount of time taken to do so. Spirometry is the first and most commonly done lung function test. It measures how much and how quickly you can move air out of your lungs. For this test, subject has to breathe into a mouthpiece attached to a recording device called spirometer, and device give data regarding respiratory functions of the subject.

Material and Method:The present study was conducted on total 112 male subjects in Ahmedabad City. Subjects were divided in

group of smokers and non-smokers, and according to their smoking habits(bidis or cigarettes) , those who were heavy smoker who smoked 20 bidis or cigarettes per day for ≥ 5 years were included in the Smokers group, , and those subjects who have not smoked any time in their lifetime, were included in the NonSmoker group. The approval of B.J.Medical College, Ahmedabad human ethics committee were obtained.

All the subjects were properly explained about the Aim and objectives, methodology, expected outcome and implications prior to the commencement of the study. Written informed consents were obtained from all the subjects. All the subjects were males. The subjects were between 20 to 60 years of age. Height and body weight was measured to calculate the body mass index (BMI). A primary screening was done to exclude gross pulmonary diseases, anatomical deformity of the chest or spine that may affect the respiratory parameters or any infective lung diseases like tuberculosis. Subjects having any known anatomical deformity of the chest or spine that may affect the respiratory parameters or any infective lung diseases or gross pulmonary diseases were excluded from the study. The subjects were further divided into smoking and non-smoking group with 50 subjects in smoker group, and

based on their smoking history, their age and BMI were matched. In smoker group, only those subjects who were heavy smokers (20 bidisor cigarettes) since last 5 years were selected. The data sheet of the subjects was collected in the form of questionnaire and was kept confidential.

Inclusion Criteria

Age 20-60 years

Smoking one pack (20 units of bidis or cigarettes per day) for ≥ 5 years (Smoker group)

No history of smoking any kind of tobacco in life time (Non-smoker group)

Exclusion Criteria

Gross Respiratory Disorders

Anatomical Deformity of Chest

Anatomical Deformity of Spine

Infective Lung Diseases

History Of Tuberculosis

Pulmonary function test (PFT), carried out with the help of The EasyOne™, 4 a handheld spirometer, which is a non-invasive and quite accurate method of assessing respiratory health status of an individual, specially the ventilation functions of lung. PFT parameters were measured by The EasyOne™ spirometer is manufactured by Medizintechnik (Switzerland). The EasyOne™ spirometer is designed for the diagnosis and management of chronic respiratory disease and asthma. The EasyOne™ is registered on the TGA and received approval from the FDA in 200010.

At the beginning, satisfactory demonstrations were given regarding the equipment and the procedure of the study. The following parameters were recorded by the computerized spirometer: vital capacity (VC), forced expiratory volume in 1st second (FEV1), peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR), FEV1 as a percentage of VC (FEV1/FVC), Mid Expiratory flow rate 75 %(MEF75), Mid Expiratory flow rate 50 %(MEF50), Mid Expiratory flow rate 25 %(MEF25). Before recording, subjects were allowed to relax. They were asked to inhale from and exhale into the disposable mouthpiece of the spirometer twice. The lips

were tightened around the mouthpiece to prevent leakage of air , as airflow must be through the mouthpiece to and from the lungs. The manoeuvres were repeated thrice and the best of the three readings was taken. At the end of the procedure , the instrument showed the detailed PFT value and readings and graphs, which were taken into consideration and noted down.

Statistical analysis: Analysis was done by applying Independent t-test by using software IBM SPSS version 21.

Result:The present study was conducted on total 112 individuals in Ahmedabad city to evaluate the effect of chronic heavy smoking the function of the Lungs.

Subjects were divided in group according to their habit of smoking those who were heavy smokers (>20 units per day) for ≥ 5 years in smoker group and, and those who has not smoked any time in their life were included in Nonsmoker group.

Table 1: Demographic data(Mean ±SD)

Parameters	NONSMOKERS (n=62)	SMOKERS (n=50)
Age	37.21±11.28	38.8 ± 9.3
Height(Cms.)	170.48±5.19	169.78±5.38
Weight(Kg.)	66.97±11.65	68.48±10.6
BMI	23.03±3.88	23.78±3.67

There was statistically no significant demographical difference between smoker and non-smoker group. Hence they were comparable for the study (TABLE 1).

Pulmonary function tests were done on all the subjects and data were compiled. Parameters which were measured by the tests are Forced Vital Capacity(FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume (1 sec)(FEV1), FEV1/FVC, Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR), Mid Expiratory Flow Rate 75%, Mid Expiratory Flow Rate 50% and Mid Expiratory Flow Rate 25%.Normality test was done on the data and Data appear to be normal

by Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. After that Independent t-test was applied on the data for measuring the difference whether it was significant or not. Results are shown in Tabular and Chart form.

Table 2 shows the results of the PFT in both Smokers and Non-smokers group. As the age group of both groups are comparable, we can rule out the effect of aging.

Table 2: Pulmonary function Tests comparison between smokers and Non-smokers Group and Statistical significance between two groups

PULMONARY FUNCTION TEST PARAMETERS	NON SMOKERS (N=62)		SMOKERS (N=50)		Independent t – test result	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	p value	SIGNIFICANT (YES/NO)
FVC OBSERVED (lit/sec)	3.58	0.59	3.25	0.53	0.004	YES
FVC PREDICTED (%)	86.59	12.06	81.50	13.64	0.038	YES
FEV1 OBSERVED (lit/sec)	2.43	0.68	2.20	0.45	0.045	YES
FEV1 PREDICTED	71.88	18.89	65.26	12.81	0.036	YES
FEV1/FVC OBSERVED	0.75	0.41	.63	0.12	0.045	YES

FEV1/FVC PRED (%)	86.83	19.46	79.03	18.76	0.034	YES
PEFR OBSERVED (lit/sec)	3.95	0.99	3.49	1.16	0.026	YES
PEFR PREDICTED (%)	56.98	20.31	48.34	19.38	0.024	YES
MEF 75 OBSERVED (lit/sec)	3.32	1.52	3.08	1.16	0.360	NO
MEF 75 PREDICTED (%)	44.91	22.81	49.42	21.50	0.289	NO
MEF50 OBSERVED (lit/sec)	2.57	1.27	2.63	1.02	0.798	NO
MEF 50 PREDICTED (%)	52.66	26.16	54.22	20.24	0.730	NO
MEF25 OBSERVED (lit/sec)	1.12	0.53	1.08	0.64	0.754	NO
MEF25 PREDICTED (%)	51.37	24.40	50.64	27.07	0.880	NO
VC OBSERVED (lit/sec)	3.29	0.77	3.03	0.58	0.048	YES
VC PREDICTED (%)	81.67	16.33	76.24	11.52	0.049	YES

SD=Standard Deviation

As if the aging affects the Lung functions then both the group of the study would have the similar data of the pulmonary function test parameters. And it's clearly found in our study that Major parameters like FVC, FEV1, FEV1/FVC, PEFR are affected in the chronic heavy smokers. It has been found in our study that, there is difference in the values like FVC, FEV1, FEV1/FVC, PEFR are lower in chronic heavy smokers statistically significantly than Non-smokers.

Discussion: Our finding suggest that there is significant difference in the Pulmonary Function test parameters among the chronic heavy smokers from non smoker. There is significant decline in the PFT values like FVC, FEV1, FEV1/FVC and PEFR, clearly stating that there is decrease in the functionality of the normal lungs in smokers. Smoking causes fatal diseases to develop in many parts of the body including cancers of the upper and lower respiratory tracts (mouth, nasopharynx, larynx, and lung), the oesophagus, and the kidney.⁵

Smoking also increases the risk of cardiovascular disease, aortic aneurysm, Crohn's disease, gastric and duodenal ulcers, cataracts, and age-related macular degeneration (causing a loss of central vision)⁵

The two most common respiratory diseases caused by smoking are lung cancer and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD).

Tobacco smoke contains chemicals in the form of particulate substances and gases. A number

of the substances found in tobacco smoke are known human carcinogens.⁵ Environmental tobacco smoke (ETS) contaminates indoor air in homes and workplaces.⁴

Constituents of tobacco smoke cause damage throughout the respiratory tree from the main airways (bronchi) to the peripheral airways (bronchioles), right down to the terminal alveoli (air pockets), as well as to the immune system. Loss of cilia and mucous gland hypertrophy occur in the upper airways; inflammation, epithelial changes, fibrosis and secretory congestion occur in the peripheral airways, and alveoli are destroyed with loss of gas exchange surface area and airways flexibility.

There are vascular changes to the small arteries and capillaries of the bronchioles and the alveoli. Smoke also causes inflammation⁶ of the cells of the bronchial tree leading to squamous metaplasia (a precancerous condition), smooth muscle hypertrophy, and peribronchial fibrosis.⁵ Damage is evident in the results of bronchoalveolar lavage .

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease COPD is characterised by airflow obstruction. This obstruction is usually progressive, not fully reversible, and does not change markedly over several months. And the smoking is found out to be one of the leading cause of the COPD.⁷

Study done by Beck GJ et al⁸, Smoking and lung function, Residual lung function (observed-predicted) was examined in these groups for forced expiratory volume in one second (rFEV1)

and for maximal expiratory flow rates at 50% and 25% of the vital capacity. Mean residuals by sex, age, and smoking category were compared and revealed an increasing progression of lung function loss with advancing age in males and females in all smoking categories. These age-related trends were due primarily to the amount smoked by persons in each group. The age of onset of these abnormalities was found to be as early as the age group 15 to 24 yr. Abnormalities were greater in smokers than ex-smokers, even when the amount smoked was taken into account.

Higgins MW et al⁹ conducted study 'Smoking and lung function in elderly men and women' and they found Lung function was related inversely to pack-years of cigarette use. Prevalence rates of impaired lung function were highest in current smokers and lowest in never smokers.

Only Fletcher et al¹⁰ and Peat et al have reported quantitative estimates of the association between the numbers of cigarettes smoked and the rate of decline of FEV₁ in a regression model adjusting for age and, in the study of Fletcher et al, for mean FEV₁/height. Their study was carried out in a middle aged male population in London and the study of Peat et al in a population aged 20 years or older in Western Australia.

Chhabra SK et al¹¹ found in their study that lung function of asymptomatic nonsmokers was consistently and significantly better among both male and female residents of the lower-pollution zone. Present study is corroborative with few of the previous studies^{1,3,8,9,12,13}, indicating significant decrease in the lung functions¹² due to heavy and chronic smoking.

Conclusion: Study concluded that smoking, as damaging the respiratory system, thereby affecting the Pulmonary function test of the chronic heavy smokers and it can be considered one of the major risk factor for chronic disorders of the lung like COPD and Carcinoma of Lung. Hence, we can say that those major

chronic fatal disease can be prevented drastically by avoiding the smoking habits and creating the awareness in the general population especially in youth, about the hazards of smoking. Conflict of interest: No conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise are declared by the others.

Acknowledgement: We are indebted to Cipla Pharmaceutical Company for providing the Spirometer for our study. We are also grateful to our subjects who shared their precious time and valuable and personal information to us.

References:

1. Buist AS, et al Effects of cigarette smoking on lung function in four population samples in the People's Republic of China. The PRC-US Cardiovascular and Cardiopulmonary Epidemiology Research Group. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 1995 May;151(5):1393-400.
2. Nicholas R, Anthonisen, John E, Connett, Robert P, Murray Smoking and Lung Function of Lung Health Study Participants after 11 Years *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*, 2002, Vol. 166, No. 5, pp. 675-679.
3. Peat JK, Woolcock AJ, Cullen K. Decline of lung function and development of chronic airflow limitation: a longitudinal study of smokers and non-smokers in Busselton, Western Australia. *Thorax.* 1990 Jan;45(1):32-7.
4. Niche Medical, EasyOne Spirometer [Internet]. Niche Medical. Available from: http://www.nichemedical.com.au/web/frames/nddTECH_frame.html [Accessed 4th April 2007].
5. Dawn Milner, *Respiratory Care Knowledge* June 2004 Vol 100 No 24, P-56
6. Higgins MW, Keller JB, Metzner HL, Smoking, socioeconomic status, and chronic respiratory disease. *Am Rev Respir Dis.* 1977 Sep;116(3):403-10.
7. Comstock GW, Brownlow WJ, Stone RW, Sartwell PE. Cigarette smoking and changes in respiratory findings. *Arch Environ Health* 1970;21:50-57.

8. Beck GJ, Doyle CA, Schachter EN. Smoking and lung function. *Am Rev Respir Dis*. 1981 Feb;123(2):149-55.
9. Higgins MW, Enright PL, Kronmal RA, Schenker MB, Anton-Culver H, Lyles M. Smoking and lung function in elderly men and women. The Cardiovascular Health Study. *JAMA*. 1993 Jun 2;269(21):2741-8
10. C Fletcher, R Peto - *British medical journal*, 1977, The natural history of chronic airflow obstruction. *Br Med J* 1977;1:1645
11. Chhabra SK, Chhabra P, Rajpal S, Gupta RK. Ambient air pollution and chronic respiratory morbidity in Delhi. *Arch Environ Health*. 2001 Jan-Feb;56(1):58-64.
12. Maritta S Jaakkola, Pierre Ernst, Jouni J K Jaakkola, Lucy W N'gan'ga, Margaret R Becklake , Effect of cigarette smoking on evolution of ventilatory lung function in young adults: an eight year longitudinal study, *Thorax* 1991;46:907-913
13. Woolf CR, Zamel N. The respiratory effects of regular cigarette smoking in women. A five-year prospective study. *Chest* 1980;78:707-13.
14. Scott T. Weiss,¹ Mark J. Utell,² and Jonathan M. Samet, Environmental Tobacco Smoke Exposure and Asthma in Adults. *Environmental Health Perspectives* (impact factor: 7.04). 01/2000; 107 Suppl 6:891-5.

Source Of Financial Support- Nil

Conflict Of Interest- None
